

COESO

connecting research and society

COLLABORATIVE ENGAGEMENT ON SOCIETAL ISSUES

WP3 - Development of the Virtual Ecosystem for
Research Activation (VERA)

D3.6. VERA widget

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VERA widget

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I. Executive summary

This document accompanies the release of the “D3.6 - VERA Widget” which is due in June 2023 as output of “Task 3.5 VERA widget development”.

The aim of this task is to develop a widget in order to promote the VERA platform on various external websites and enhance user onboarding through direct call-to-action features. This widget has been specifically developed as a WordPress plugin.

Its primary purpose is to encourage user engagement and communication externally to the platform and to onboard new users on VERA. Initially, the widget is being seamlessly integrated into external platforms, with a strong focus on WordPress integration, particularly targeting the backend of the OpenEdition platform Hypotheses.org, which has over 35000 users and over 7000 blogs.

I. Structure of the document

This document is structured in III sections:

- Section I: Executive summary
- Section II: Description of the VERA widget
- Section III: Conclusions

II. VERA Widget

In this section it is described the VERA Widget design and implementation.

As anticipated in the introduction the VERA widget has been designed as a Wordpress plugin targeting, as a first step, the backend of the Hypotheses.org blogging platform, which is run by the French national research infrastructure OpenEdition¹ and hosts over 35000 users and over 7000 blogs.

The widget has been implemented in order to display live updates from the VERA platform when editors access their back-office on Hypotheses.org. In order to maximise the visibility, the widget will be turned on by default on all blogs, giving users the possibility of deactivating it as shown in the picture below:

Figure 1 - Plugin activated by default in the backend

¹ <https://www.openedition.org/>

Technically speaking the plug-in will retrieve data from the vera.operas-eu.org server by querying a public REST API² answering on the standard 443 (HTTPS) port.

No data from VERA will be posted/put to the blog server, just a GET HTTP³ calls will be performed to get data.

From an implementation perspective, it would be very useful to track if a user arrives on VERA via the widget: for this purpose Mixpanel⁴ will be used.

The plugin has been developed with the aim of ensuring full compatibility with the Wordpress updates.

In terms of production, the plugin has been developed but not yet integrated into Hypotheses.org. This decision has been taken in order to avoid any possible issue in the July/August period when people might be on vacation and not ready to tackle possible issues promptly. A testing plan will be created and stress testing on the API call will be conducted.

Once it is approved by the technical team of Hypotheses.org, the widget will be launched in production ideally early in September.

In terms of look and feel, the plugin has been designed with the aim to attract people on the VERA platform, therefore it has an introductory text and displays the most recent projects as shown in the following picture (Figure 2). The plugin has been designed in order to be fully responsive (Figure 3).

Figure 2 - Widget view

² <https://www.redhat.com/en/topics/api/what-is-a-rest-api>

³ <https://developer.mozilla.org/en-US/docs/Web/HTTP/Methods/GET>

⁴ <https://mixpanel.com/>

Activate research!

VERA is an online hub facilitating and promoting participatory research involving social sciences and humanities research. Join its vibrant community of citizen science practitioners! Connect with partners, organize your project's digital tools, and find funding. VERA development is coordinated by OpenEdition, powered by operas-eu.org.

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Figure 3 - Responsive view

III. Conclusions

Overall, the design and implementation of the VERA Widget as a WordPress plugin demonstrates careful consideration of user experience, data security, compatibility, and tracking capabilities.

In terms of design it has been developed as a WordPress plugin, initially targeting the backend of the Hypotheses.org blogging platform, which is operated by OpenEdition and has a large user base.

The widget's purpose is to display live updates from the VERA platform when editors access their back-office on Hypotheses.org. By default, the widget will be activated on all blogs, with users having the option to deactivate it if desired.

The plugin retrieves data from the vera.operas-eu.org server by making GET HTTP calls to a public REST API. No data from VERA is posted or put on the blog server, ensuring data security and privacy. It has been developed with a focus on ensuring full compatibility with future WordPress updates. It has also been designed to be fully responsive, adapting to different screen sizes and devices for an optimal user experience.

The design aims to attract users to the VERA platform. It features introductory text and displays the most recent projects, utilising a visually appealing layout. The plugin's responsiveness ensures a seamless experience across different devices.

As future evolution, it would be good to be able to develop an iframe⁵ style plugin that allows to promote a single project or the VERA platform in general on the frontend of external blogs and websites without any compatibility issues.

⁵ https://www.w3schools.com/tags/tag_iframe.ASP